

Explained in 60 Seconds: Astronomy communication careers and how to make them more sustainable

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During a panel discussion at the Communicating Astronomy with the Public (CAP) 2024 conference, the community reflected on careers in astronomy communication, from profiles and networking to entry-level positions and career progression. As the community strives to professionalise the field of astronomy communication, it is imperative to find a definition as open and culturally sensitive as possible of what an “astronomy communicator” is, keeping in mind that people often come into the field with more than one academic or practice background. This brings a wide variety of skills and interdisciplinary teams essential to astronomy communication’s growth. Recognition, funding, accreditation, networking and support are among the pillars the panellists identified that we should build upon to create a stronger and more sustainable astronomy communication community.

Introduction

The field of astronomy communication has significantly grown over the past 15 years, since the International Year of Astronomy 2009, with new institutional actors and a wider cohort of professionals joining the community internationally. Science communicators, public engagement specialists, outreach professionals, educators, and journalists are examples of the many profiles in such a varied and multifaceted domain, each underpinned by specific education and training paths (*Anjos et al., 2021*). However, opportunities for aspiring astronomy communicators are still few and far between. Too often, the information flow regarding existing job openings remains limited to institutions that are proactive in the field. Overall, two major barriers remain to professional progress: first, to enter into the field, substantial experience is often required, and later, to find long-term or permanent positions, which are few and far between. This was the theme of a plenary panel discussion held during the CAP 2024 conference in Toulouse, France, attended in-person and online by roughly 300 astronomy communication professionals from more than 50 countries. The panel invited the community to collectively reflect and take action on these open issues of relevance not only to the community itself but also to the wider body of astronomers and stakeholders and, ultimately, to the public as well. Four panellists joined the

discussion: Audrey Korczyńska (Territoire de Sciences), Kelly Blumenthal (IAU Office for Astronomy Outreach), Oana Sandu (Science Wave) and Samir Dhurde (Inter-University Centre for Astronomy and Astrophysics).

Networking vs. volunteering

As shared by the panellists – four professionals spanning a variety of roles, backgrounds and experiences – the entry point to astronomy communication jobs is often through networking, mentoring or volunteering. Encounters with inspiring, generally more senior colleagues who are active in outreach and communication, for example, during graduate school, can be hugely influential, prompting individuals to follow in their steps and disseminate the same “spark” towards the fascination for the cosmos. Such occasions, however, rely on chance. The scarcity of role models and visible profiles in astronomy communication and outreach may hamper imagination: most people can hardly see this as a viable career choice. In addition, several organisations tend to rely on volunteers for many of their public engagement activities. While this has proved an actual way to enter the community and gain valuable skills, it is certainly not an option for a large number of aspiring astronomy communicators, especially those coming from the most marginalised backgrounds, as opposed to paid internships (*Muñoz-Mateos et al.,*

2024), which unfortunately are very scarce in the field of astronomy communication. The emphasis on volunteering also reduces the perceived value of these careers and their professionalism in the eyes of institutions, researchers and aspiring communicators.

Who is an astronomy communicator?

The beauty of a rich and diverse community such as ours cannot easily be constrained by a clear set of skills and qualifications. A live survey of the audience during the panel discussion in Toulouse polled the background of participants, both in person and online: more than half of the 153 respondents (around 55%) declared having an astronomy background, followed by general science (15%), communications (11%), education (5%), humanities (5%) and other (9%). The request immediately prompted a question: which field should be indicated when one has multiple backgrounds, as is common in this community? For example, someone may have a degree in astronomy and a specialisation in communications and/or education. In most interdisciplinary endeavours, such as astronomy communication, it is best to have a team of people with multidisciplinary backgrounds, bringing together people from fields such as public relations, science, graphics, and copywriting, and in so doing, exchanging

retention within our professional field. As visually represented in Figure 1, the most frequently indicated words were recognition, interdisciplinary, funding, accreditation, internships, networking, open mind and support, followed by several urgent suggestions such as professional development, upward job mobility, training, and mentorship. Indeed, preliminary results from a survey investigating issues and barriers in astronomy communication careers⁴ indicate that major challenges are insufficient funding, finding suitable professional development opportunities and the scarcity of senior and/or permanent positions in the field. A common response also refers to the overall lack of recognition that this is a viable professional career path that requires various skills and continuous training and should, in turn, be rewarded with pay grades and job security (whereas in most cases, astronomy communicators in scientific institutions have a different job placement than their fellow researchers). To move forward, we as a community must strive for enhanced inward communication, widespread mutual respect between communicators and institutions, and a truly collaborative approach to teamwork, priorities and funding. With that, we will be much better suited to tackle some of the most pressing questions about life and the cosmos – and engage communities worldwide in the project of science.

Notes

¹ More information about Open Badges can be found here: <https://openbadges.org/>

² Some examples of public engagement training include the Kavli-IAU training resources, *Public Engagement and Engaging the Public*, found here: <https://www.iau.org/news/announcements/detail/ann22008/>. Additionally, the IAU Office of Astronomy for Development has created a public engagement training course through The Open University that can be found here: <https://www.open.edu/openlearncreate/course/view.php?id=3071>

³ In 2024, C. Mignone began a project to track jobs in astronomy communication: <https://astronomyoutreachjobs.wordpress.com>

⁴ Readers can participate in the survey on careers in astronomy communication by clicking this link: <https://forms.gle/XAYcSFzYBgzx6kyo7>

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Biographies

Claudia Mignone is an astronomer and science communicator at the Italian National Institute of Astrophysics (INAF), where she writes and edits content and creates new outreach resources to share the beauty of the cosmos with the public and broaden access to scientific culture. Before that, she worked for ten years as a science communicator at the European Space Agency (ESA).

Jorge Rivero González is an astronomer and science communicator and the Head of the Communication and Outreach Office of the Institute of Space Sciences (ICE-CSIC) in Spain. Before that, he coordinated the IAU centenary celebrations in 2019 and participated in the global organisation of the UN's International Year of Light and Technologies based on Light 2015 and UNESCO's International Day of Light. Since 2009, he has been a member of the science outreach programme GalileoMobile.